

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER'S OPINION TOWARDS CELEBRITY BRAND ENDORSEMENT WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

In today's world celebrities act as major opinion leaders and since awareness levels about MNC's brand are low, celebrities play a major role in brand recall. Despite the obvious economic advantage of using relatively unknown personalities as endorses in advertising campaigns, the choice of celebrities to fulfill that role has become common practice for MNC's brand competing, in today's cluttered media environment. Because of their high profile, celebrities may help advertisements stand out from the surroundings clutter, thus improving their communicative ability. Celebrities have always been the easiest way for a new product launch and will remain to do so in the near future on account of their man appeal. India has opened he markets only recently for celebrity endorsement, witnessing a massive growth in their sales and profit. They have seen that the correct choice of a celebrity can surely increase sales but when it comes to long term loyalty and impact on the brand. Hence, the right use of celebrity by MNC's can escalate the unique selling preposition of a brand to new heights.

Key Words: Celebrities, Clutter & Profit

Introduction:

Celebrity branding or celebrity endorsement is a form of advertising campaign or marketing strategy used by brands, companies, or a non-profit organization which involves celebrities or a well-known person using their social status or their fame to help promote a product, service or even raise awareness on environmental or social matters. Marketers use celebrity endorsers in hopes that the positive images of the celebrity endorser of the brand will also be passed on to the products or the brand image associated with the celebrities. Celebrity endorsement is usually commonly used by fashion or beauty brands, but a non-profit organization relies on celebrities as well, as celebrities have mass communication skills which can attract people's attention and is helpful in reaching a wider audience to raise their awareness towards a certain organization or an issue. Thus, making celebrities effective fundraisers.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the type of celebrity mostly preferred by respondents.
- ✓ To find out the opinion of respondents towards the celebrity endorsers of MNC's brand.
- ✓ To examine whether the celebrity promote the image of MNC brand.
- ✓ To examine whether the celebrity endorser can influence the purchase intention of customers.

Review of Literature:

Michael A. Kamins, Meribeth J. Brand (et al) (2013), In their study "Two-sided versus One-sided Celebrity Endorsements", examines celebrity endorsements in advertising using a two-sided framework, in terms of the internalization and identification processes of social influence. Result shows that when compared to a traditional one-sided celebrity endorsement, the two-sided communication elicited significantly higher advertising credibility and effectiveness ratings, higher evaluation of the sponsor in terms of perceived overall quality of service, as well as a significantly greater intention to use the advertised service. These findings suggest that the use of a celebrity appeal in a two-sided form is an effective advertising strategy.

Area of the Study:

The area of the study is limited to Coimbatore city. It is popularly known as Manchester of south India, is situated in the western part of the state Tamil Nadu.

Scope of the Study:

In today's world, the use of celebrity endorsements for MNC's advertisement has become a trend and a perceived winning formula of corporate image building and product marketing. Celebrity endorsement enhances brain recall and creates a very favorite impact on the consumers. MNC's all over the world have always paid big bucks to celebrities as their endorser involved to have a famous face associated with their products. In a globalize world it is frequently used approach in marketing for all brand's building exercises.

Research studies have proven that the MNC's brand can very quickly establish the creditability and can get an immediate identification by the use of celebrity endorsers in the advertisements. An effective way to

promote the MNC brand products is only through celebrity endorsements. Market survey had revealed that Asian market favours celebrity endorsements as a major driver towards the brand building activity. Hence it is appropriate to make a study on attitude of consumers towards MNC's brand with celebrity endorsement.

Statistical Tools Used:

- ✓ Percentage Analysis
- ✓ Chi-Square Test

Limitations:

The study is limited to 100 respondents only. These 100 respondents cannot represent the whole population in the Coimbatore city. Only top five Celebrity endorsers and their products were taken because of the time constraint.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Age of the Respondents:

Age	Respondents Percentage
Below 20 Years	13%
21-30 Years	62%
31-40 Years	7%
Above 40 Years	18%
Total	100%

The above table shows that 62% of the respondents are between the age group of 21-30years, 13% of the respondents are below 20years and 7% of the respondents are between the age group of 31-40years.

Gender of the Respondents:

Gender	Respondents Percentage
Male	54%
Female	46%
Total	100%

The above table shows that 54% of the respondents are Male and 46% of the respondents are Female.

Marital Status of the Respondents:

Marital Status	Respondents Percentage
Single	70%
Married	30%
Total	100%

The above table shows that 70% of the respondents are Single and 30% of the respondents are Married.

Occupation of the Respondents:

Occupation	Respondents Percentage
Student	40%
Businessman/Women	18%
Professional	28%
Others	14%
Total	100%

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that 40% of the respondents are Students, 18% of the respondents are Businessman / women and 14% of the respondents come under the category of others.

Income Level of the Respondents:

Income Level	Respondents Percentage
Below 10,000	4%
11,000-20,000	19%
20,000-30,000	35%
No Earnings	42%
Total	100%

The above table shows that 42% of the respondents have No earnings, 19% of the respondents income level is between 11000-20000 and 4% of the respondents income level is below 10000.

Kind of Celebrity that the Respondents Like the Most:

Kind of Celebrities	Respondents Percentage
Sports	38%
Cini Stars	43%
Politicians	3%
Others	16%
Total	100%

The above table shows that 43% of the respondents like Cini Stars, 16% of the respondents prefer Other's and 3% of the respondents like politicians.

Awareness of the Products by the Respondents:

Options	Respondents Percentage
Yes	72%
No	28%
Total	100%

The above table shows that 72% of the respondents are aware of the products and 28% of the respondents are not aware of the products.

Association between Age and Opinion of the Respondents about Huge Money Used By MNC for Celebrity Endorsement:

Null Hypothesis:

Ho: "There is no significant association between Age and Opinion of the respondents about huge money used by MNC for celebrity endorsement."

Factors	Chi Square Value	P. Value	Significant / Non Significant	Accepted / Rejected
Opinion	27.295	0.522	Non Significant	Accepted

Note: S – Significant (p value $\leq$ 0.05), NS – No Significant value (p value > 0.05)

From the above table it is clear that calculated value for Opinion (0.522) is greater than the table value (0.05). So, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hence, it can be concluded that there is no significant association between Age and Opinion about huge money used by MNC for celebrity endorsement.

Association between Occupation and Celebrity that the Respondents Like Most:

Null Hypothesis:

Ho: "There is no significant association between Occupation and Celebrity that the respondents like most."

Factors	Chi Square Value	P. Value	Significant / Non Significant	Accepted / Rejected
Occupation	27.925	0.528	Non Significant	Accepted

Note: S – Significant (p value $\leq$ 0.05), NS – No Significant value (p value > 0.05)

From the above table it is clear that calculated value for Occupation (0.528) is greater than the table value (0.05). So, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hence, it can be concluded that there is no significant association between Occupation and Celebrity that the respondents like most.

Findings:

- ✓ Majority (62%) of the respondents are between the age group of 21-30years.
- ✓ Majority (54%) of the respondents are Male.
- ✓ Majority (70%) of the respondents are Single.
- ✓ Majority (40%) of the respondents are Students.
- ✓ Majority (42%) of the respondents have No earnings.
- ✓ Majority (43%) of the respondents like Cini Stars.
- ✓ Majority (72%) of the respondents are aware of the products.
- ✓ Majority (44%) of the respondents prefer Internet as a media for branding.
- ✓ Majority (32%) of the respondents opinion is "Quick connects and higher degree of re-call towards Celebrity endorsers with MNC brand.
- ✓ Majority (84%) of the respondents agree that the Celebrity endorsers appeal to the MNC targeted audience.
- ✓ Majority (86%) of the respondents feel that only Virat Kohli is Suitable for the Product he Endorse.
- ✓ Majority (24%) of the respondents are neutrally emotional attached to the MNC brand using favourite celebrities.
- ✓ Majority (38%) of the respondents opinion is PUMA about huge money used by MNC for celebrity endorsement.
- ✓ Majority (42%) of the respondents Agree that Celebrity endorser as a tool to achieve salient and brand super stardom.
- ✓ Majority (70%) of the respondents will purchase the products if a new celebrity endorse them.
- ✓ Majority (74%) of the respondents Agree on the Effectiveness of Celebrity Endorsement.
- ✓ Majority (51%) of the Respondents Preference is Neutral, towards the Celebrity Endorsers not Associated with Another Product.
- ✓ Majority (40%) of the respondents have No idea, when Celebrity Endorser involve in Public scandal or Die.

- ✓ Majority (52%) of the respondents Disagree, towards the Celebrity themselves using the product which they endorse.
- ✓ It is concluded that there is no significant association between Age and Opinion about huge money used by MNC for celebrity endorsement.
- ✓ It is concluded that there is no significant association between Occupation and Celebrity that the respondents like most.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Celebrity endorsement used by MNC's will be more effective. When used consistently overtime to increase the strength of the link between the celebrity and endorsed brand.
- ✓ Test the potential brand/celebrity combinations to ensure that the impression and image of the celebrity is positive for the target audience.
- ✓ Celebrity endorses can be used effectively reinforce and create an image for a product/service.
- ✓ Celebrity endorses will be more effective for MNC's brand for which consumers have limited knowledge/facts.
- ✓ Brand managers should select the celebrities based on the positioning of the MNC brand.
- ✓ Celebrity endorsement will be more powerful when using a celebrity with a high "fit or belongingness" with the endorsed MNC brand.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that celebrities have always been the easiest way for a new product launch and will remain to do so in the near future on account of their man appeal. India has opened he markets only recently for celebrity endorsement, witnessing a massive growth in their sales and profit. They have seen that the correct choice of a celebrity can surely increase sales but when it comes to long term loyalty and impact on the brand. Hence, the right use of celebrity by MNC's can escalate the unique selling preposition of a brand to new heights.

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